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THE CONCEPT OF MARKETING AT IT INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract. Currently, a new stage is being formed in the development of the digitalization processes of the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is based on the transition of the economy to market conditions of operation, achievements in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT), as well as accumulated experience in their application in various spheres and sectors of the national economy. The article examines the modern meaning of marketing, as well as the concept of marketing activities from an enterprise in the context of digitalization of the economy.

Keywords: digital economy, marketing, from the enterprise, marketing automated information system, market, system analysis

Introduction

Currently, a fundamentally new situation is emerging in the field of informatization and all types of communication. Thus, information and the sphere involved in its transformation is becoming the largest factor in the scientific, technical and socio-economic development of all sectors of the economy.

In order for industrial enterprises to function and develop in the existing difficult economic conditions, it is necessary to make rational use of market mechanisms, principles and methods of studying market conditions, the theory of strategic

planning, and a set of measures to effectively influence the strengthening of their competitive positions. The leading role here is played by marketing, which determines the strategy and tactics of enterprises based on the study of consumer demand.

In a broad sense, marketing is a system for organizing and managing all the activities of an enterprise for the development, production and sale of goods or services based on the integrated use of the market and real customer requests. The marketing system makes the production of goods dependent on

consumer demands, its leading role is to balance production and demand for goods [1].

The need to apply the marketing management concept in the global economic system has become especially noticeable due to the intensification of competition. Marketing significantly increases the validity of decisions made on all issues of scientific, technical, industrial, financial and marketing activities, extending to a certain extent the planning functions to the sphere of market relations. The tasks and functions of marketing in each enterprise are subject to change. In particular, F. Kotler notes: "Marketing is an area of rapid obsolescence of political attitudes, strategies and programs [2]. Each firm should periodically reassess its overall approach to the market, using a technique known as marketing revision." Therefore, the marketing strategy should be based on a long-term forecast, and tactics should include a study of current market conditions based on the principles of a market economy.

Currently, almost all industrial enterprises have established departments (services) dealing with marketing issues, or existing sales departments of finished products are charged with market research functions. These divisions and services are equipped with modern computing equipment, staffed with personnel of various specialties, among which there are still few qualified marketers. The work carried out by these departments on market research, market poverty search, including the collection and processing of marketing information, is, as a rule, one-sided, episodic and essentially not systematized. Solving local tasks using personal computers, which are now mostly purely reference, cannot provide the desired effect. In order to effectively apply the marketing concept, it is necessary to have a developed, stably functioning information system (IS).

At the same time, the level of automation of product design, production and management at enterprises is significantly lower than in developed countries.

Literature Review

By organizing marketing services (departments, bureaus, groups), business leaders generally understand that the current dynamics of market processes determines the need for a systematic approach to management and the use of new information technologies. The need to create marketing automated information systems (MAIS) is primarily related to the fact that information in marketing is of key importance, since activities focused on meeting the needs of society are based on accurate knowledge of the specific situation in the market [3].

Although this fact is obvious and generally recognized, there are only general recommendations in foreign and domestic literature on the construction of conceptual MAIS models. There are no answers to the questions that constantly arise in practice: What is the functional structure of such an information system? What tasks should it solve? What specific methods and models are used in it?

It is obvious that MAIS belongs to the class of large and complex systems. It is known that a large and complex system is characterized by the following features: the possibility of dividing the system into many subsystems, the goals of which are subordinated to the general purpose of the functioning of the entire system; the presence of an extensive network of complex information links between elements and subsystems; the interaction of the system with the external environment; functioning under the influence of external and internal factors; the presence of a hierarchical structure.

All these signs are characteristic of MAIS, and they must have such basic indicators of the quality of functioning as [4]: 1) efficiency (the ability to fulfill its goal in the best possible way); 2) reliability (the ability to function in case of failure of its individual elements); 3) stability (the ability to maintain the required properties under conditions of exposure various disturbances).

When researching, analyzing, designing, implementing and operating MAIS, it is necessary to take into account the listed features and quality indicators of complex systems. Special attention should be paid to accounting and analysis of the

interrelationships and interactions between the elements and links of the information system, between the system itself and the external market environment. The solution of these issues in the construction, implementation and operation of MAIS, of course, should be carried out using a systematic approach generally recognized in the methodology of modern scientific knowledge of complex systems.

One of the main actors in the digital economy is an IT industry enterprise, for which today it is not so much the desire to reduce production costs that is most important, as the ability to sell a higher-quality software product or one with some new properties to the consumer. At the same time, the requirements for the production of PP are constantly increasing, due to the following reasons [5]:

- serious competition in the market of software products and services, which has radically changed the attitude to product quality;

- high production flexibility, which allows you to quickly change the range of software product, which is associated with a significant reduction in their life cycle and an increase in diversity;

- the uncertainty of the external environment, primarily in the sense of changes in state economic policy, as well as the rapid and flexible reorientation of production and sales by competitors;

- the increasing complexity of business digitalization technology;

- changing the structure of production costs.

Traditionally, the effective operation of the enterprise consisted of the following components [6]:

- 1) execution of planned tasks (not necessarily directive ones);

- 2) compliance with the required technical, economic and aesthetic characteristics of the products;

- 3) product compliance with reasonable consumer requirements;

- 4) ensuring the competitiveness of goods in the domestic and global markets;

- 5) reducing the number of defects and failures of products during operation.

Based on this, the purpose of production was formulated as the timely fulfillment of obligations for

supplies in the established nomenclature, in the required quantity and quality, while minimizing the costs of design, technical preparation of production and directly for the production of software product itself.

The dynamic change in technology, the struggle for consumers and product quality, and the growth of competition force enterprises to consider the whole range of management issues in a new way. Focusing on consumer demand, conducting a maneuverable scientific, technical and commodity policy, and striving for innovation have become the main ideas of the new management philosophy [7].

Materials and methods

Currently, there has been a change in the stereotypes of managerial thinking, conceptual approaches to enterprise management. Of course, modern management methods do not completely reject the rationalistic model, which was and remains the methodological basis for the formation of organizational structures, planning, research, and economic calculations [8]. Elements of strict administrative management remain preferable in certain conditions, requiring, for example, rapid concentration of attention on any area of work or when solving specific production tasks. If the company operates in conditions of fierce competition, increased risk, when new ideas are constantly needed, purely administrative methods are ineffective. In this case, flexible management is required, focused on the creative manager.

In modern management, it is customary to distinguish three main types of activity:

- 1) Technical activities for the creation and development of new products, the use of advanced types of materials, equipment, and technologies in the production. The main thing in this area of activity is the birth of a new idea;

- 2) Management activities to coordinate actions, ensure the order and consistency of production processes. Here, success is achieved by the ability to get results through the efforts of subordinates (management itself is the management of internal factors);

3) Management activities for the organization of the company's actions in the market of goods and services (a system of strategic management of the company's activities in the market). It has received a special name – marketing management activity, in other words – enterprise management based on external factors.

Marketing and management are two inseparable and interrelated aspects of enterprise management, with the first acting as a generator of ideas, and the second is designed to ensure their achievement [9].

Results

Currently, there are five main approaches on the basis of which companies conduct their marketing activities [10]. These approaches are reflected in the table.1. The marketing concept can be presented as follows (Fig.1.). If an enterprise operates according to such a scheme, then we can say that the marketing concept operates on it. Considering this scheme, it is necessary to highlight three main points:

1. All efforts of the enterprise's entrepreneurial activity are aimed at the consumer.
2. It should be recognized that the buyer, who has certain needs and requirements, knows how to satisfy them.
3. The purpose of the enterprise is to satisfy the needs of the buyer and, depending on the degree to which this goal is achieved, his income is determined.

Table 1.
The concept of marketing activities of enterprises in the field of information technology

<i>The concept</i>	<i>The essence of the concept</i>
The concept of production improvement	Consumers will be sympathetic to products that are widely distributed and affordable. The management apparatus should improve production and increase the efficiency of the distribution system
The concept of product improvement	Consumers will be supportive of products with the highest quality. The

	company should focus its efforts on the continuous improvement of the product
The concept of intensification of commercial efforts	Buyers will not buy the company's goods in sufficient quantities unless it makes significant efforts in the field of sales and incentives
The concept of social and ethical marketing	The task of the enterprise is to identify the needs, needs and interests of the target markets and ensure the desired satisfaction in effective ways while preserving the well-being of the consumer and society as a whole
Marketing concept	The key to achieving the company's goals is to identify the needs of target markets and ensure the desired satisfaction in ways that are more effective than those of competitors.

It is the concept of marketing that is currently most widespread.

Fig.1. The scheme of the marketing concept

With a focus on marketing, sales staff become one of the main ones in the management system, because their task is to ensure uninterrupted, efficient operation of the enterprise in difficult conditions of a market saturated with software products. It is a saturated market, when the supply of sellers exceeds the demand of buyers, that is the main condition for applying the marketing concept and ensuring its

effectiveness, since in this case significant costs for market research, for stimulating measures and for creating special marketing services are justified.

Marketing as a concept of management of market-oriented production and sales and scientific and technical activities is one of the most important areas of an integrated management system for all aspects of an enterprise's activities, exerting an increasingly active influence on them, including supply and demand analysis, management of production and economic activities, financial management, logistics system [11]. At the same time, it defines the structure of the information system, personnel policy, representing a multi-level and multifunctional complex aimed at meeting human needs.

The company's management should not passively observe the development of events in the market, but should actively influence the needs of society, thereby forming the market. Schematically, this requirement is illustrated in Fig.2.

Fig.2. Interaction of the enterprise with the market

The need for an enterprise to actively influence the market is dictated by the presence of competing products on it, as well as a reduction in their life cycle. Therefore, competing enterprises are forced to constantly strive for an innovative breakthrough that provides long-term competitive advantages.

Discussions

Summarizing the experience of applying the concept of marketing in enterprises in the field of software products and services, we can formulate the following marketing postulates that managers and marketers should be guided by:

1. Study and identify the needs and requirements of real and potential consumers in order to meet them.

2. Produce only those software products, offer and provide only those services that are in demand.

3. Meet the requirements of your customers. Remember that the consumer (customer) is always right!

4. Create new software products (services) that will be in demand among consumers, as well as periodically update or modernize the software products (services) produced.

5. Use modern information technologies. Possession of high-quality timely information is the key to effective management.

6. Finance science, marketing research and promotion of software products (services) in the sales markets. Innovation is the basis for the development of entrepreneurial activity.

7. Expand and deepen the market for your software products (services).

8. Ensure the required level of quality of your software products (services).

9. Set prices that correspond to the quality of the software product (service) and market conditions.

10. Pay constant attention to advertising. Advertising should be memorable and pleasant for the perception of a potential buyer, arouse interest and desire to purchase the advertised software product (service).

11. By all available means, maintain and strengthen the brand (brand) of your company.

The purposeful behavior of software product manufacturers is reflected primarily in the management functions, covering the analysis of problems, planning, organization, conduct and control of measures aimed at solving these problems. The following four groups of issues are of the greatest importance for marketing activities.

First, information issues. The company needs four categories of information:

1) data on the external environment, primarily about consumers, sales intermediaries, competitors, suppliers and government actions;

2) data on the available opportunities to influence the market and create consumer preferences;

3) data on insurmountable in the near future internal restrictions of an industrial, financial, personnel and other nature;

4) data on the impact of marketing tools in a variety of environmental conditions. Currently, marketing services at the enterprise have the ability to process and analyze a larger amount of data than before, due to the rapid development of electronic data processing systems and marketing automated information systems. The process in this area is also driven by the expansion of information services provided by specialized firms.

Secondly, the issues of using marketing tools, the so-called "Marketing mix", covering four main tools: product, price, distribution, and sales promotion [9,10,11]. Knowing the realities of the market allows you to create a software product and choose the time of sale in such a way that it is possible to realize the produced quantity of goods on the terms desired by the seller. The tools of the Marketing Mix complex are fully used here:

1) working with a product is aimed at its quality, i.e. at determining, maintaining or changing its properties. This also includes the formation of a production program, the creation of new software product, the presentation of guarantees, as well as after-sales customer service;

2) pricing policy covers setting and changing prices, differentiating them, providing discounts, and agreeing on payment terms;

3) distribution includes the creation of a sales system, the choice of sales channels, the use of special sales methods;

4) Promotion and communication contains the following tools: advertising, communication message, sales support and public relations. All this is aimed at informing and activating potential buyers, convincing them of the profitability of purchasing this product and encouraging them to buy.

Thirdly, the issues of organizing marketing activities. The organization of marketing in an enterprise should be based on an information system. Naturally, at the same time, the company will only be able to implement a consistent market policy when all

services recognize the presence of marketing. If the marketing organization reaches a certain degree of development (in terms of the volume of tasks performed, the number of employees or other indicators), there is a need to structure it using certain criteria, which can be used as management functions, products, markets. There are many different types of organizational management structures focused on marketing [11,12,13,14].

Fourth, the issues of control in the field of marketing. Here we are talking about checking the correctness of the decisions made in order to draw conclusions from the deviations that have arisen between the planned and actual results. The subject of the analysis is a wide variety of aspects: products, sales channels, market conditions, advertising activities, reports of sales agents, etc.[10,11]

When developing or choosing a methodology for structuring the goals and functions of a management system, it is necessary to take into account the state of the system, the nature of the analyzed type of activity, the degree of knowledge of the object, as well as the allotted period of time for designing or improving the management system. The formalization of complex multilevel systems is very important, which allows achieving the necessary accuracy of description, applying mathematical methods and conducting structural studies. When conducting a systematic analysis of the goals and functions of marketing in an industrial enterprise, generally speaking, various techniques can be used, which are based on a combination of methods for activating knowledge, experience of specialists and methods of formalized representation of systems. The analysis of these techniques shows that the most suitable in the conditions of an industrial enterprise operating in the market is a methodology based on the concept of a system that takes into account the external environment, goal setting and relationships with the environment in the process of its functioning and development

This technique was developed and studied by F.I. Peregudov, V.Z. Yampolsky, L.V.Kochneva [8]. It is based on the definition of the V.N. Sagatovsky

system [10], namely, the S system is defined as follows:

$$S = \overset{def}{\langle A, R, Z, SR, DT \rangle},$$

where A is the set of elements of the system;

R – is the set of relations (connections) between the elements;

Z – goals of the system;

SR – is the environment in which the system is located;

DT – is the time period of the system's existence that affects the process of goal formation.

Conclusions

The adoption of such a structuring concept allows us to take into account all the essential goals, functions and tasks of marketing both within the enterprise and arising from interaction with other systems: government agencies, the current environment and subordinate structures (branches, subsidiaries, etc.). When mastering the production of new types of goods, in the event of significant external or internal disturbances, this technique focuses the researcher's attention on the need to restructure the structure of the goals and functions of the system in accordance with the current economic situation.

In the work of V.N.Volkova, it is recommended to apply this technique in the process of system development, revision of the production structure of an enterprise or its organizational management structure. The creation of MAIS requires a significant organizational and functional reorganization of the enterprise management system, which confirms the expediency of choosing this technique, the main stages of which correspond to the levels of system structuring.

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